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Road to India @100: Envisioning India in year 2047

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Abstract: India has come a long way since gaining independence in 1947 and becoming a republic in 1950. In 2047, it will have completed 100 years as a republic and it is exciting to realize what a country might look at that time. This article will discuss about the past and future progress of India. India envisions to be global leader in Innovation and Technology, to have a highly educated and skilled workforce. In addition, India wants to be centre for International Trade and Commerce. India aims to create the supportive business environment for Business world so that it attracts the investments from around the world. Thus, we can say that India vision in 2047 is for progress, prosperity, Innovations, High tech and skilled workforce and a step towards the being the Global Leader.

Keywords: Innovation, Progress, Global Leader

1. Introduction

India aims to be the model of new technology and innovation by 2047. The India aims to look itself among the top three nations. According to the scientific researcher Kalaiselvi, till 2070 the entire globe will accept India as ruling power in sciences.

India is a country of rich history, diverse culture and with great potential and has made a significant growth in various fields since its independence in 1947. By prioritizing education, innovation, and international cooperation, India has the potential to become a beacon of hope and motivation for the world. India has come a long way since gaining independence in 1947 and becoming a republic in 1950. In 2047, it will have completed 100 years as a republic, and it is exciting to think about what the country might look like then. As a nation, we have made significant progress over the past few decades, especially at the beginning of the 2000s. It is easy to imagine that in the next 25 years and make even greater strides. The country's diverse culture and rich history will continue to be a major draw for tourists, making it a top destination for cultural exchange and exploration. By prioritizing education, innovation, and international cooperation, India has the potential to become a beacon of hope and motivation for the world.

2. Research Objectives

The research objectives are given below:

- 2.1.1 To discuss about the growth prospects of India till 2047.
- 2.1.2 To discuss about the changes in Business Environment to attract the foreign investors.
- 2.1.3 To discuss about the role of government in education sector.

2.2 Research methodology

This research article is based on secondary data. The sources of data are books, journals, magazines, newspaper and websites.

Panch pran: Resolves for Developed and Resurgent India

On the completion of 75 years of independence, Hon'ble PM, Sh. Narendra Modi ji, steps towards a new direction with new resolution. He has stated five pran to move the country in the path of growth and progress. The Five Prans are:

2.2.1 First Pran: Goal of Development India: This goal of developed India discussed the journey of India from Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav to regains its position of Vishvaguru by 2047. The goal can be achieved only when every citizen of the country commits themselves to a part of this journey and make the country a developed nation. The pran is to accomplish the “Viksit” India.

2.2.2. Second Pran: Removal of any trace of colonial mindset- Looking at the past of nation, it is being observed that still we have the slave mentality and colonial mindset which haunt the psychology of the country and creates the obstacles in the growth and development of the country. The India takes the second pran to collectively get rid by themselves from any trace of colonial mindset so that nation swiftly progress towards its vision for 2047.

2.2.3. Third Pran: Take pride in our roots – Indian should always feel pride on their culture, diversity, spiritual heritage, Moral values etc. Every citizen should feel pride of being the citizen of this glorious nation and motivated towards their contribution to the growth of the economy

2.2.4. Fourth Pran: Unity – India is a diverse country but still it is a strong country due to its innate sense of unity. The sense of unity binds the people from different religion, caste and state and different culture. This sense of unity strengthens and protect the country from the disruptive elements

2.2.5 Five Pran: Sense of duty among the citizens-

Fulfilling the duties of citizens with honesty: All citizen of the country needs to carry out their duties with honesty and be a responsible citizen. This single-minded dedication to commit and strive towards fulfillment of the duties as a citizen shall form the central pillar that supports India's journey in the Amrit Kaal. The call of the Hon'ble Prime Minister on Panch Pran shall be widely circulated among the youth. They shall take the Panch Pran Pledge, while understanding the significance and committing themselves to contribute towards India's growth story in making in the age of Amrit Kaal. The India today aspires to become the Vishvaguru by attaining the heights of prosperity throughout the country. This dream is difficult but not the impossible, we all have to collectively work hard to achieve this dream. The people of India can achieve this dream under the leadership of Prime minister Narendra Modi. It is being observed that there has been multiple economic challenges and covid attack which has given the severe setback to Modi government, but the government has been able to take a major moves in all spheres of education, health, agriculture to new technology, society upliftment to strong foreign relations. Today India has attained the name, fame and respect at the global level. The domination and influence of India is increasing due to Narendra Modi's policies, politics, economic and peaceful coexistence ideology which is evidenced by the fact that it is for the first time that a government promotes Yoga, Ayurveda, Food, Literature, Tradition, Knowledge and Experience not only at home but across the globe. Last but not the least India's age's old philosophy emphasizes on being in contact with the entire existence and aiming at greater consciousness. India has been a source of knowledge for world civilization since the beginning.

3. Envision India in 2047 and its thrust area of development

In 2047, India will be a country that will be thriving in every aspect of life. It will have successfully harnessed the power of technology, innovation, and education to transform itself into a global leader. The government will be proactive in addressing the needs of its citizens and will have implemented policies that ensure the overall well-being of the population.

3.1. Thriving Infrastructure

One of the most striking features of India in 2047 will be the rapid development of infrastructure. The country will have a well-connected network of roads, railways, and airports, making it easy for people to travel within and abroad. The government will have to invest heavily in developing smart cities, which will be equipped with state-of-the-art amenities and facilities. These cities will be designed to be energy-efficient and environmentally friendly, making them ideal places to live and work. India is also building the modern digital infrastructure. Technologies like 5G and Artificial intelligence are used to transform areas like medicine, education, agriculture and many other sectors. Modern technologies will help to form the base of **One Nation One Ration** and JAM (Jhan Dhan Yojna, Aadhar and Mobile Number). The new digital technology will help in bringing the benefit directly to the poor people.

3.2 Accessible Healthcare

In terms of healthcare, India in 2047 will be home to some of the best hospitals and medical facilities in the world. The government will have to prioritized healthcare and implement the policies that make it accessible to all citizens. Many trained medical professionals, including doctors, nurses, and specialists, will work in the public and private sectors to provide top-quality care to patients.

Today India has earned a global respect by becoming the largest producer of generic medicines and vaccine supplier. The country has launched Ayushman Bharat PMJAY which is world largest public health scheme and covering 50% of people in the country. The model Public –Private Partnership (PPP) models has gained the success in India’s healthcare especially during the period of COVID-19, has created an opportunity of providing the affordable and accessible healthcare to all the people. The government aims give a holistic and personalized touch to healthcare sector and work on neglected areas like geriatric health and mental health.

3.3 Improved Education

Education will also be another area where India will have to make significant progress. The government will have to invest heavily in developing schools and universities, and there will be many highly qualified teachers and professors who will be helping to shape the minds of the next generation. A wide range of educational resources will be available to students, such as books, computers, and other technological aids, which will enhance their learning. The first step towards achieving the goals of HEI by 2047 is redesigning the higher education institutions (HEI) architecture and develops the student centric education system. The NEP 2020 is a detailed framework for transforming education in India. It is focusing on critical thinking, holistic development and global perspectives.

3.4 Thriving Economy

One of the most notable features of India in 2047 will be its thriving economy. The country will have a diverse range of industries, including manufacturing, agriculture, and services, contributing to its rapid growth. Many successful businesses will operate in the country, and the government will implement policies that encourage entrepreneurship and innovation. It is forecasted that India will be the fastest growing large economy aiming a six folds increase in its per capita GDP that would cross US\$ 15, 000 in the 100th year of independence. The Eight key enablers of growth have been identified that will play a critical role in enhancing the growth engine of the country. These enablers are:

3.4.1 World’s Information Technology and Services Hub: India has an opportunity to fill in the talent gap as developed economies face a shortage of skilled talent due to demographic changes. This would be in areas such as education and healthcare, where services are increasingly being delivered over digital channels. India has the potential to become a services and technology talent hub for the world.

- 3.4.2 Digitalization: A Force Multiplier:** The furious pace of digitalization in the country, including by the government, would result in multiple benefits of improving governance, financial inclusion and providing a framework for private players to reach new markets and create new products and services. The India Stack pioneered in the country is now the global benchmark for most countries. Following a spate of digitalization in the government and private sectors, the digital economy has grown by 15.6% over the period 2014 to 2019, 2.4 times faster than the growth of the Indian economy. Platforms like Open Credit Enablement Network (OCEN) and Open Network for Digital Commerce (ONDC) will democratize credit at scale and e-commerce market respectively.
- 3.4.3 Filing the credit gap to fuel growth:** India's private debt to GDP ratio remains one of the lowest among large economies, providing a headroom to drive 200 – 300 bps incremental annual GDP growth for the next 20-30 years to reach the current global average private debt to GDP levels. With accelerated credit growth and development of the corporate bond market and digital lending, an optimal financial architecture can help address the critical demand and supply gap in credit to individuals and Micro Small and Medium Enterprises ("MSMEs"), reduce cost of capital, and increase the share of private debt to sustain high growth.
- 3.4.4 Thriving entrepreneurship spurred by private capital:** Start-ups have grown remarkably over the last six years, with India emerging as the third largest ecosystem for start-ups globally. Private Equity/Venture capital investments in India have touched record levels, reaching US\$82b in FY21-22. The spurt of new-age companies across technology and other sectors on the back of rapid digitalization, large domestic market and strong capital availability will be instrumental in delivering relatively high and sustained growth to the Indian economy.
- 3.4.5 Making domestic manufacturing competitive:** As global supply chains continue to diversify post pandemic, the government's 'Aatma nirbhar Bharat' (self-reliant India) initiative in manufacturing has found further impetus through path-breaking policies such as the Production-Linked Incentives (PLI). Going forward, the country has the opportunity to move up the value chain through complex, high value product manufacturing and in emerging "sunrise" sectors of semiconductors, mobile phones and EVs, positioning India as a nucleus of manufacturing for the domestic and global markets.
- 3.4.6 Transition to sustainable energy:** The government has set a target to be net zero by 2070 and reduce carbon intensity by 45% by 2030 vis-à-vis 2005 levels. Renewable energy and development of green hydrogen can help India in its endeavor to achieve energy independence by reduced hydrocarbons import. The goal has announced several progressive policies toward adoption of green hydrogen, with a goal to meet 10% of global hydrogen demand by 2030. The policy changes have spurred investments by both the private sector and state-owned enterprises providing optimism that round the clock emission-free energy may become a reality.

3.5 Strong International Relations

In terms of international relations, India in 2047 will be a respected member of the global community. The country will have strong diplomatic ties with many countries and will be a key player in regional and international organizations. It will have also taken a leading role in addressing and tackling major global challenges, such as climate change and terrorism. It will be working closely with other nations to find solutions to these pressing issues. Prime Minister Narendra Modi has set the target of turning India into a developed nation by the 100th year of India's independence, 2047. He also aims to remove the corruption and nepotism from the country.

3.6. Embracing Technology and Innovation

Bharat was known for many inventions and scientific discoveries like **Agriculture, Astronomy, Architecture, Metallurgy, Mathematics, and Medicine**. Moreover, the Indus Valley Civilization has many magical creations like healers curing tooth disorders with bow drills, water-flushed toilets, sophisticated sewage system, all this in 7000 BC. But, not limited to this, our Bharat invented yoga, a tool to transform humans for global good, the first cataract surgery, chess, snakes, and ladders (An excellent learning tool that teaches the ups and downs of life), Cashmere Wool and others. Bharat's GDP in 1000 AD was around 29% of Global GDP.

Bharat, in the past, never documented its inventions and discoveries. This may be because learning and teaching philosophy in those times differed fundamentally. Teachers/gurus/experts speak, and students listen and enhance their knowledge. There were no documents to refer to; hence, students in the class required hyper attention and active listening. All the past discoveries were in the brains of the inventor others know when the inventor shares them. This may be one of the reasons we fail to prove to the world our past inventions, as science today expects documented proofs. Now the country has moved to the path of technology and innovation. It is promoting young scientist and young minds towards innovation and technology development. India in 2047 will be a nation that has embraced technology, innovation, and education to drive its growth and development and will be well-positioned to take on future challenges.

The India will be completing its 100th year of independence in 2047 and the projections shows that India is on the path of becoming the second largest global economy by 2047. The country could see its spending power grow from just 3 percent of a US consumer today to 24 percent by 2050. The consumer and retail market could approach \$6 trillion, and financial services will be the most active sector in the world, home to an estimated 300 billion transactions. The country will also be more educated and more modern. There will be an estimated 600 million students in India in 2047 and some 1.5 billion Internet users—both representing the world's largest markets of these respective sectors. And in the auto industry, 75 percent of new passenger vehicle sales will be electric, with the country home to potentially half a billion electric vehicles. This outlook suggests unprecedented opportunities for businesses to scale in India by 2047 and for global champions to emerge from the ranks of India's corporations.

4. Conclusions

India always amazes the entire world as a nation with 140 cr people living in a country with **ONENESS** with 1000s of languages, cultures, traditions, attires, and cuisines. Yet, it is incredible, with this much diversity; the oneness differentiates us from the rest of the world. For 1000s of years, the living philosophy of Bharat is **not to harm others**, and happiness is within the human and not outside; the people in Bharat respect and devote **Nature**, a living ecosystem of birds, animals, forests, soil, water, air, and fire, as the creator. This is the only nation that considers the human body a temple and does not need to go to temples separately. That means this nation advocates for each human to see their inside and enhance their consciousness (awareness) so that they never harm others, become kind, speak only the truth, and work hard in a very structured manner. Now the country is on the path of moving from developing country to developed country. For India to achieve the goal of being a developed nation, we need to harness the full potential of our current demographic dividend. Today, India's gross enrollment ratio in higher secondary education is around 50 per cent. It means we are only unleashing half the potential of our youth; the other half is not being skilled through formal education. This needs to change significantly. Mere efficient utilization of natural resources through cheap labour will not be sufficient. Pioneering a knowledge economy—a system of consumption and production that is based on intellectual capital—is the need for a better tomorrow. The knowledge economy can be a huge enabler going forward to drive growth.

The economy of 2047 would be more balanced with a higher share of manufacturing. India should have attained leadership in key segments like renewable energy, electronics, chemicals, textiles, automotive and pharmaceuticals. India should lead the way through a focus on high quality and application of cutting-edge technology and design. While we think of national-level goals and enablers, it is also important for the mining and metals industry to achieve its true potential. The steel industry in India today largely caters to the growing domestic market. Despite having the key raw materials required for steelmaking, we are not one of the top exporters of steel and related downstream products. China, Japan and South Korea are the top exporters of steel globally despite having raw material disadvantages. This is an opportunity which we could capitalize on. We need to also work towards breakthroughs in sustainability practices. We have an opportunity to not only grow but to lead the green transition. We have had some unique challenges throughout our history but have always overcome them and thrived. We have displayed unparalleled tenacity and resilience. We have done this consistently despite our incredible diversity of culture, language and geography. In fact, these have been our strengths and there is a bond of “Indianness” that binds us together. We have exhibited this for the past 75 years with success, and we will continue to do so. A vibrant democracy is what makes India. This is what will build the India we wish to see at 100.

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